

Evaluation of the Performance of English Teachers in the Secondary Stage in View of Marazano Evaluation Model and its Relation to Some Variables

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Abstract: The present period is identified with knowledge expansion and information upheaval, which consequently put new responsibilities in the education system that must be in charge with preparing qualified individuals having the ability to fulfill the technical and cognitive requirements. Teachers are one of the important elements of accomplishing the goals of the educational system since they actually implement the educational policies in society. Moreover, they hold the obligations of transforming values, standards, and general purposes of behavioral processes encompassing the necessary steps for preparing new educated generations. Thus, the educational system is preoccupied with the proficiency of the teacher, his skills, capacities, leadership, and professional level in teaching, as well as his abilities and qualifications enabling him to carry out all the required obligations in his career.

Keywords: Evaluation, performance, stage, Marazano, relation.

تقويم اداء معلمي اللغة الانجليزية في المرحلة الثانوية في ضوء نموذج تقييم مارازونا وعلاقته ببعض المتغيرات

ملخص الدراسة: تتميز الفترة الحالية بالتوسع المعرفي والاضطراب المعلوماتي، مما يفرض مسؤوليات جديدة على نظام التعليم والتي يجب أن تتولى إعداد أفراد مؤهلين لديهم القدرة على تلبية المتطلبات الفنية والمعرفية. يعد المعلمون أحد العناصر المهمة لتحقيق أهداف النظام التعليمي حيث أنهم ينفذون فعلياً السياسات التعليمية في المجتمع. كما

تقع على عاتقهم واجبات تحويل القيم والمعايير والأغراض العامة للعمليات السلوكية بما يشمل الخطوات اللازمة لإعداد أجيال جديدة متعلمة. ومن ثم فإن النظام التعليمي يهتم بكفاية المعلم ومهاراته وقدراته وقيادته ومستواه المهني في التدريس، فضلاً عن قدراته ومؤهلاته التي تمكنه من القيام بجميع الالتزامات المطلوبة في حياته المهنية.

الكلمات المفتاحية: التقييم، الأداء، المسرح، مارزانو، العلاقة.

INTRODUCTION

The teacher is the tutor, coordinator, and facilitator of the educational process which is intended to accomplish the educational purposes, including ideas, capabilities, opinions, moral qualities and behavioral strategies; so, teacher's evaluation is a vital domain of educational assessment. This significance comes from the importance of the teacher's role in the educational system. It is important to assess the teacher's performance to build up all his capacities by offering numerous chances for continuous learning to accomplish brilliant performance (Hariri, 2007).

The concerned people or organizations in education perceive that the profession of the teacher nowadays are not the same as those of the last times and that his obligations in the future are distinguished from today's since these assignments or obligations are created in the system by the cognitive expansion witnessed by the teacher and the student. In this sense, assessing the performance of the educator is an essential method for recognizing how far the teacher knows about his responsibilities and the level of his proficiency.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In spite of the development of educational research in the field of the teacher's performance evaluation, and the emergence of many studies that called for the need to evaluate the performance of the

teacher in recognition of his important role in the success of the education and the achievement of educational goals, the development of the teacher's performance and the improvement of his competency is of utmost importance and cannot be ignored. This is done only with an effective system of evaluating the performance of the teacher and identifying strengths and weaknesses in this performance and development. Still, there are deficiencies in the evaluation of teachers when it is conducted by the school administration alone as it is not enough to judge the performance of the teacher. Hence, the researcher adopted the evaluation of the teachers of English in the light of the Marzano Model- one of the modern global trends in the Preparation and evaluation processes of the teacher with correlations to some variables.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study draws on the importance of the evaluation process of teachers in general and of English teachers in particular by implementing a proposed card designed to evaluate the performance of English language teachers based on the global model of evaluation "Marzano Evaluation" the researcher can summarize the importance of the study in the following points:

- This study provides the ministry of education with a realistic picture of the most important teaching skills that English teachers lack of light,. Of each of the areas/domains of the questionnaire at English teacher performance level according to Marazano evaluation model to be adopted within the programs of teacher preparation, induction, orientation and training.

- This study opens new horizons to the ministry of education to use modern models to evaluate the performance of teachers.

PURPOSES AND THE QUESTION OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to define the measuring the performance, the degree of the secondary stage English language teachers in Irbid, first directorate in the field of strategies and classroom behaviors according to the Marzano evaluation model.

- Measuring the degree of teaching performance of the secondary stage English language teachers in Irbid, first directorate in the fields of preparation and lesson planning according to the Marzano evaluation model.
- Measuring the degree of teaching performance of the secondary stage English language teachers in Irbid, first directorate in the field of critical thinking according to Marzano evaluation model.

Realizing the individual differences of statistical significance between the study sample members' responses, i.e. differences attributed to the study variables (gender, years of experience, educational qualification).

The purpose of this study can be achieved through answering the following questions:

- Q1: What is the level of performance of secondary stage English teachers in the directorate of Irbid, first according to Marzano's teacher evaluation model (in relation to each of the 4 domains of the model and the model as a whole)?
- Q2: Are there any statistically significant differences in ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the averages of the performance of the secondary

stage English teachers in the directorate of Irbid, first on the Marzano scale attributed to the gender, years of experience and educational qualification?

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS OF TERMS

Evaluation of the Performance:

Stufflebeam (2000). The assessment is a professional activity that individual teachers should do in case they plan to explore and improve the learning they are trying to simplify constantly.

The researcher defines Evaluation is a systematic process that involves a variety of activities. Teachers gather information about student achievement informally and formally. Informal evaluation is used by the teacher to provide feedback to students and to check for understanding of the teaching and learning process.

Marzano Evaluation Model:

Marzano's causal teacher evaluation model (herein called the Marzano teacher evaluation model) depends on his acclaimed art and science of teaching system, which characterizes instructional procedures distinguished by research to increase the student learning results. The Marzano teacher evaluation model nearly lines up with teaching criteria for achievement and a student data module that binds the student accomplishment to the instructor assessment through employing information nearer to the classroom. The objective of a successful assessment system is for instructors to incrementally build their skills in teaching year to year and, consequently, incrementally increase their capacity to raise the students' learning results year to year.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter is divided into two parts: theoretical framework and review of related literature.

● Theoretical Framework

The primary purpose of teacher evaluation is personal and professional growth that leads to improved performance.

Teacher evaluation has historically addressed two objectives:

- Improving performance (the evaluation is part of a continuous improvement cycle designed to help the teacher).
- Bringing about the dismissal of those judged as inadequate or nonproductive.

If we hope to dramatically improve our schools, the two purposes of evaluation must remain distinct, and the teacher should never have any doubt about which purpose is driving an evaluation (Marzano, Gaddy, Foseid. (2005)).

While Danielson and Mc Greal. (2000) claim that the purpose of educator assessment is too:

- Measure the efficiency of every educator.
- Arrange and rank teachers& reward educators as the best or high position.
- Enhance the learning, abilities, skills, and classroom practices of expert teachers.
- To refine their teaching abilities; basically examine their own performance and their students' performance too.
- Conduct the developments required to enhance educating and learning.

- Performance assessment systems offer the required assistance, supply, and development chances in light of the instructors' individual requirements, and also those of their students, schools, and provinces.

In spite of the fact that endeavors to move rapidly in outlining and performing more efficient instructor assessment systems are worthy, we have to recognize a vital issue-that estimating educators and improving educators are diverse purposes with various results. An assessment system outlined basically for estimation will seem to be very unique from a system planned principally for advancement. For achieving the success of the instructors' assessment, the attention must be paid to individual and expert development that stimulate and enhance performance. At the point when fear exists or when educators realize assessments as little more than "hoops" to be jumped through, there is for all intents and purposes zero chance for assessment to be valuable. Our educators and students are worthy of an assessment system that enhances instructor's performance and students' learning (Helmi & Fouad. (1991)).

The Marzano teacher evaluation model is a result of a large number of studies conducted in the course of recent decades, and published in numerous books that have been utilized by instructors and distinguishes it from some other educator assessment models completing inside the classroom- the methodologies and practice educators use to improve student accomplishment.

The objective of a successful assessment system is for educators to incrementally build their skills in instructing year to year and,

subsequently, incrementally increase their capacity to raise the students' learning results year to year.

- **DOMAINS & ELEMENTS OF THE MARZANO TEACHER EVALUATION MODEL:**

The Marzano teacher evaluation model contains sixty items designed to inform the instructional practices of teachers. There are forty-one items in domain 1, eight in domain 2, five in domain 3, and six in domain 4. The specifics of each domain are outlined below (Marzano, Frontier, & Livingston. (2011)).

Domain 1: Classroom Strategies and Behaviors

This domain focuses on pedagogical strategies that impact student achievement. Domain 1 addresses what teachers do in the classroom: It reflects the intricacy of what happens during any given lesson and the natural flow of activities.

The model is based on the premise that lessons are constructed with multiple parts and that each part of a lesson has distinct characteristics, routines, and processes. A model built to support teachers as they develop their skills must necessarily reflect the complexity of their work.

The forty-one of the sixty items in the model is from domain 1, the model clearly emphasizes what occurs in the classroom, which differentiates it from some other teacher evaluation models. This domain contains not only the largest number of strategies, but also those that have been shown in causal studies to have the most direct effect on improving student performance.

The forty-one items in domain 1 are divided into three segments:

- Segments involving routine events (contains 5 items).

- Segments addressing content (contains 18 items).
- Segments enacted on the spot (contains 18 items).

Domain 2: Preparing and Planning

This domain focuses on planning and preparing, four units of instruction and lessons within units, both of which are assumed to be directly linked to classroom strategies and behaviors. Careful planning and preparation give a teacher enough time to incorporate effective classroom strategies and behaviors. The better a teacher prepares, the more effective are his or her instructional choices.

The eight items in domain 2 are divided into three categories:

- Planning and preparing for lessons and units (contains 3 items).
- Planning and preparing for the use of materials and technology (contains 2 items).
- Planning and preparing for the special needs of students (contains 3 items).

Domain 3: Reflecting on Teaching

This domain focuses on deliberate practice. It encourages teacher self-reflection in the areas of evaluating personal performance and developing and implementing a professional growth plan.

When teachers receive specific and focused feedback using a common language of instruction, they increase their experience and subsequently, student performance. And this domain focuses on teacher self-reflection, a vital met cognitive step in teacher development.

The five items in domain 3 are divided into two categories:

- Evaluating personal performance (contains 3 items).

- Developing and implementing a professional growth plan (contains 2 items).

Domain 4: Collegiality and Professionalism

This domain is the backdrop for the other domains and encourages a supportive culture. It addresses collegiality and professionalism, emphasizes opportunities to observe and discusses strategies. It supports teacher's participation in lesson study, instructional rounds, teacher-led professional development, and professional learning communities in which teachers collaboratively examine evidence of student learning and the impact that specific instructional strategies have on learning.

These behaviors are only indirectly linked to classroom strategies and behaviors; however, they make up the foundational expertise from which the preceding three domains can flourish.

The six items in domain 4 are divided into three categories:

- Promoting a positive environment (contains 2 items).
- Promoting the exchange of ideas and strategies (contains 2 items).
- Promoting district and school development (contains 2 items).

Reviews of Related Literature:

Al-Zahrany (2017) Efficiency of Marzano's Learning – Dimensions Paradigm in Promoting Levels of Reading Comprehension at Third Grade Intermediate Students, the study followed the descriptive as well as the experimental methods, with the latter approach based on the experimental / control groups procedure. To analyze the data obtained, the researcher employed the statistical techniques: frequencies; percentages; arithmetic means; standard deviations,

independent samples T Test; Levens' Test to measure homogeneity and Ancova test.

The study arrived at specifying (16) reading comprehension competencies needed by third class intermediate students. The results obtained in the study revealed the existence of statistically significant differences at the level (0.001) between the two controls and experimental groups in the post -achievement score means in the reading comprehension test at the five levels (literal, deductive, critical, appreciative, and creative) in favor of the experimental group students. These findings emphasize the learning dimensions model of Marzano in developing reading comprehension levels of third grade intermediate students with a value reaching (3.01) which is a large value indicating the existence of the practical significance of the study's results. The study made a number of recommendations for people charged with the task of planning Arabic language curricula at the Education Ministry, in addition to Arabic language teachers and supervisors. The study proposed the conduct of some researches relevant to its topic.

Ali & Jerri (2017) The effect of a Marzano 's model of distance learning in the acquisition of first - grade students is the average of the temporal concepts of history. The research aims at finding out the effect of Marzano's model of distance learning in the acquisition of first grade students with the average temporal concepts of history. In order to achieve the objective of the research and its hypothesis, the researchers adopted the experimental approach and a number of procedures that include the determination of experimental design and the research society. The sample of the research was 70 students

distributed equally into two groups (experimental and control, 35 students in each group, were chosen by the simple random, . In addition to achieving the objective the two researchers developed the test of temporal concepts prepared by Ali Kayed Khreisha, 1997, and adapted by researcher Shaima Al-Sultan, 2004, after deleting, adding some paragraphs and extracting his sincerity by presenting it to the experts and arbitrators, As well as extract its stability and the power of excellence.

After correcting the answers and processing the data statistically, the results showed that the students in the experimental group studied the history of ancient civilizations according to Marzano's model of distance learning for the students of the control group who studied the same subject according to the usual method of testing the temporal concepts. Research The researchers reached a number of conclusions, recommendations and proposals that would develop the teaching of history in the intermediate stage.

Al-Deyy (2017) The effect of using Marzano's model of the dimensions in the teaching of spherical geometry on the achievement and the development of mathematical thinking skills of the tenth grade Gaza province and students attitudes towards it. The study used a quasi-experimental approach, and to achieve the objectives, the tools comprised a teacher's guide, achievement tests and mathematical thinking and trends. The study sample consisted of 62 students of tenth grade in Gaza province. They were divided into two groups: the first group was an experimental group of (31) and the other was a control group of 31 students, and after that the data and information were collected and analyzed statistically.

The most important findings of the study were that there is a high effect of the dimensions of learning in Marzano's form on both achievement and mathematical thinking skills and the improvement of students' attitudes positively towards mathematics information and statistical analysis, and that there is a high effect of the dimensions of learning related to Marzano's form on both achievement and mathematical thinking skills as well as the improvement of students' attitudes positively towards mathematics.

DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

This chapter includes the procedures followed throughout the study. It introduces a complete description of the methodology of the study, the population and the sample and the instrumentation. Moreover, it introduces the appropriate statistical treatment for the study.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The Population of the study consisted of (172) teachers of all English teachers in the secondary stage in the directorate of Irbid first during the second semester 2018/2019.

SAMPLE OF THE STUDY

The sample of the study comprised of (169) English teachers in the secondary stage in the directorate of Irbid first during the second semester 2018/2019. Distributors according to the table (1):

Table (1) Distribution of study sample by gender, years of experience and educational qualification

Variable	Category	#	Percentage
Gender	Male	74	43.8%

	Female	95	56.2%
Years of Experience	Less than 5	59	34.9%
	5 – 10	79	46.7%
	More than ten years	31	18.3%
Educational Qualification	BA and Below	98	58.0%
	Above BA	71	42.0%
Performance	High	55	32.5%
	Average	68	40.2%
	Low	46	27.2%
Total		169	100.0%

INSTRUMENT OF THE STUDY

To measure the evaluation of the performance of English teachers in the secondary stage in the view of questioner according to the Marzano evaluation model and its relation to some variables

The researcher designed a questionnaire to evaluate the Performance of English teachers in the secondary stage in the view of the Marzano evaluation model. The card consisted of four domains “Classroom Strategies and Behaviors, Preparing and Planning, Reflecting on Teaching, Collegiality, and Professionalism” There are forty-one items in domain 1, eight in domain 2, five in domain 3, and six in domain 4 (Appendix I).

VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY OF THE INSTRUMENT

To ensure the Validity of the instrument, it was presented to a jury of (5) specialists in the fields of applied linguistics methods of teaching English language.

Reliability of the instrument was verified by calculating the statistical parameter of the alpha-Cronbach test on a sample of (15) teachers (not included in the study). The value of the internal stability coefficient (Alpha) was. 91 for the total of the instrument. The reliability coefficient for all dimensions ranged from 72.1 - 86.2, which is a high and positive discrimination. And the reliability of the instrument was computed using the test/ retest method. The reliability of estimates were as follows in Table (2).

Table (2) Alpha-Cronbach reliability of the instrument

N	Domains	Reliability
1.	Classroom strategies and behaviors	.72
2.	Preparing and planning	.84
3.	Reflecting on teaching	.81
4.	Collegiality and professionalism	.86
	Total	.91

Miller, 1998) indicated that the correlation coefficient above 60% is a high stability coefficient. Accordingly, all correlation coefficients in this study are higher.

The questionnaire to evaluate the performance of English teachers in the secondary stage in the view of the Marzano evaluation model includes four domains.

The four domains of the questionnaire to evaluate the performance of English teachers contain 60 items, each of which builds on the others to support teacher growth, development, and performance explain in Table (3)

Table (3) The domains and elements of the questionnaire

Domains	Elements
1. Classroom strategies and behaviors	41
2. Preparing and planning	8
3. Reflecting on teaching	5
4. Collegiality and professionalism	6
	Total 60

The responses to paragraphs are distributed as follows: Always (4), Usually (3), Sometime (2), Never (1), and to judge the level of performance on Marzano's teacher evaluation model, used the following:

- From 1-less than 2/ Low
- From 2 – less than 3/ Medium
- 3 and above/ High

It is calculated by:

- $4-1=3$ / Indicated to the three levels.
- $3/3=1$ / Is the value which added.
- Then editing (1) from the lower limit for the category.

Statistical Treatment

To answer the study questions, the researcher used the statistical analysis program (SPSS), using the following statistical methods:

- Arithmetic mean and standard deviation to answer the first question.
- Tree Way ANOVA analysis, to answer the second question.

RESULTS, DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this chapter, the researcher offers the results according to the statistical analyses of the collected data. The findings of the research were tackled with regard to the research questions. Therefore, the researcher employed different statistical formulas to show the final results of the collected data.

- **Results of the Study**

In this section the researcher presented the results of the study through answering the questions of the study:

- Q1. What is the level of performance of secondary stage English teachers in the Directorate of Irbid, first according to Marzano's teacher evaluation model (in relation to each of the 4 domains of the model and the model as a whole)?

To Answer the question Mean & Standard deviation for domains & the total of the instrument as seen in table (4):

Table 4 Mean & standard deviation for domains & the total of the instrument

Domains	Mean	St. D	Rank	Level
Classroom strategies and behaviors	2.61	0.15	2	Medium
Preparing and planning	2.61	0.35	3	Medium
Reflecting on teaching	2.62	0.40	1	Medium
Collegiality and professionalism	2.58	0.38	4	Medium
Total	2.60	0.12	-	Medium

As shown in table 4 the level of performance of secondary stage English teachers in the Directorate of Irbid, first according to Marzano's teacher evaluation model who comes medium to mean= (2.60) and standard deviation= (0.12), and the domain (Reflecting on teaching) comes at the first rank, with mean= (2.62) and standard deviation= (0.40), where the domain (Collegiality and professionalism) comes at the last rank with mean= (2.58) and standard deviation= (0.38). Attributed to the school focusing on students' achievement as an essential factor in evaluating personal performance of the teacher and his ability to develop and execute the plans.

Below is a presentation of the means and standard deviations of the items of each domain:

The Classroom Strategies and Behaviors Domain

Table 5 Mean & standard deviation of the classroom strategies and behaviors domain

No	Items	Mean	St. D	Rank	Level
22	Engage students in complex tasks (decision-making, problem-solving, experimental- inquiry, and investigation tasks) that require them to generate and test hypotheses.	2.76	1.02	1	Medium
28	Maintain a lively pace by moving between students to ask, answer, and evaluate questions and answers.	2.73	1.03	2	Medium
31	Provide opportunities for students to talk about themselves.	2.71	1.07	3	Medium
10	Provide strategies to help student's process new information.	2.67	1.05	4	Medium
12	Record and Representing Knowledge by allowing a student to acquire, organize, and retain content knowledge.	2.67	1.08	5	Medium
25	Use games that focus on academic content that is providing a fun way	2.67	1.06	6	Medium

	for students to deepen their learning.				
26	Manage response rates by engaging students in answering questions and participating in class discussions.	2.67	1.04	7	Medium
29	Demonstrate intensity and enthusiasm using instructional strategies.	2.67	1.08	8	Medium
16	Use Homework to provide students with the opportunity to extend their learning outside the classroom.	2.66	1.01	9	Medium
21	Encourage them to take new information that students have deep knowledge of, and applying it in a different context.	2.65	0.99	10	Medium
32	Present intriguing information to make positive discussion skills among students.	2.65	1.05	11	Medium
36	Give students the opportunity to reflect on their personal interests and share them with you.	2.65	1.02	12	Medium
27	Bring physical movement into the classroom to encourage class interaction.	2.64	1.10	13	Medium
30	Use friendly controversy between teacher and students, and students themselves.	2.64	1.05	14	Medium

35	Acknowledge adherence to rules and procedures.	2.63	.99	15	Medium
1	Determine the objectives of each class accurately	2.62	.99	16	Medium
6	Helping students to know what is critical in your classroom by identifying critical information.	2.62	1.07	17	Medium
17	Examine Similarities and Differences by determining his strong and weak points for students.	2.62	1.05	18	Medium
18	Help students to revise their understanding by examining errors in reasoning.	2.62	1.05	19	Medium
37	Use various verbal and nonverbal behaviors that indicate affection for students.	2.62	1.05	20	Medium
40	Make sure low-expectancy students are asked challenging questions at the same rate as high-expectancy students.	2.62	1.04	21	Medium
23	Use the supporting tools in achieving the lesson goals.	2.61	1.04	22	Medium
8	Previewing New Content by Provide students with positive experiences about the lesson before starting it.	2.60	1.00	23	Medium
20	Revise knowledge by helping students to compare their initial	2.60	1.04	24	Medium

	knowledge about the topic with what they now know.				
13	Reflect on Learning by allowing students to step back from their learning experience to help them develop critical thinking skills and improve on future performance by analyzing their experience.	2.59	1.03	25	Medium
19	Help students develop proficiency by practicing skills, strategies, and processes	2.59	1.08	26	Medium
33	Provide opportunities for students to talk about themselves by limitation of student interests and makes connections between these interests and class	2.59	1.03	27	Medium
39	Demonstrate value and interact positively with low expectancy students.	2.59	1.09	28	Medium
9	Chunk information into pieces containing more concepts and information than the students can readily process.	2.58	1.03	29	Medium
34	Reinforce adherence to rules and procedures as opposed applying consequences for lack of adherence.	2.58	1.03	30	Medium
5	Providing students with the	2.57	1.08	31	Medium

	instructions and procedures of the class.				
14	Provide many diverse opportunities to review students learning before moving on to new content.	2.57	1.05	32	Medium
24	Monitor individual student engagement.	2.57	1.05	33	Medium
7	By relating the new lessons with the previous ones	2.56	1.06	34	Medium
4	Preparing assignments that meet the objectives of the lesson.	2.53	1.09	35	Medium
38	Behave in an objective and controlled manner with students to make a trusting relationship with your students.	2.52	1.07	36	Medium
2	Evaluate students' performance through participation	2.51	1.04	37	Medium
3	Motivate student achievements in the classroom.	2.49	1.07	38	Medium
41	Break a question into smaller and simpler parts and ask low-expects students to further explain their answers.	2.49	1.03	39	Medium
11	Elaborate on New Information by giving students opportunities to elaborate on knowledge.	2.48	1.07	40	Medium

15	Organize students to practice and deepen knowledge through understanding content at a higher level of accuracy.	2.44	1.05	41	Medium
	Total	2.61	0.15	-	Medium

As shown in table 5 the item number (22) which “Engage students in complex tasks (decision-making, problem-solving, experimental-inquiry, and investigation tasks) that require them to generate and test hypotheses.” comes at the first rank with mean=(2.76) and standard deviation=(1.02), While the item number (15) which “Organize students to practice and deepen knowledge through understanding content at a higher level of accuracy.” comes at the last rank with mean=(2.44) and standard deviation=(1.05). Attributed to engaging students in complex tasks is essential to test hypotheses about new knowledge.

The Preparing and Planning Domain

Table 6 Mean & standard deviation of the preparing and planning domain

<i>No</i>	<i>Items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>St. D</i>	<i>Rank</i>	<i>Level</i>
44	<i>Pay attention to established content standards by connecting curricula with reality.</i>	2.70	1.07	1	Medium
46	<i>Employ technology to achieve the lesson goals by using available technology.</i>	2.66	1.05	2	Medium

42	<i>Prepare the organization of content in such a way that each new piece of information builds on the previous piece.</i>	2.64	1.10	3	Medium
43	<i>Plan and preparing for lessons and units.</i>	2.60	1.12	4	Medium
47	<i>Supporting English language learners by meeting their needs.</i>	2.60	1.09	5	Medium
48	<i>Provide a friendly –environment for the needs of students receiving special education in a regular classroom.</i>	2.59	1.08	6	Medium
45	<i>Use of available resources to achieve the objectives of the lesson.</i>	2.57	1.06	7	Medium
49	<i>Plan and prepare for the needs of students who lack support for schooling.</i>	2.53	1.03	8	Medium
	<i>Total</i>	2.61	0.35	-	Medium

As shown in table 6 the item number (44) which “Pay attention to established content standards by connect curricula with reality.” comes at the first rank with mean= (2.70) and standard deviation= (1.07), while the item number (49) which “Plan and prepare for the needs of students who lack support for schooling.” comes at the last rank with mean= (2.53) and standard deviation= (1.03). Attributed to established content standards by connecting curricula with reality

encourages students to organize each new piece of information built on the previous piece.

The Reflecting on Teaching Domain

Table 7 Mean & standard deviation of the reflecting on teaching domain

No	Items	Mean	St. D	Rank	Level
51	Evaluate the effectiveness of individual lessons and units of instruction in terms of enhancing student achievement and identifies causes of success or difficulty.	2.69	1.08	1	Medium
53	Develop a written professional growth and development plan with specific and measurable goals.	2.67	1.08	2	Medium
52	Evaluate the effectiveness of specific strategies and behaviors by providing a written analysis of specific causes of success or difficulty.	2.63	1.02	3	Medium
54	Monitor progress relative to the educational development plan.	2.60	1.06	4	Medium
50	Analyze and prioritize strengths and weaknesses of students.	2.53	1.03	5	Medium
	Total	2.62	0.40	-	Medium

As shown in table 7 the item number (51) which “Evaluate the effectiveness of individual lessons and units of instruction in terms of enhancing student achievement and identifies causes of success or difficulty.” comes at the first rank with mean= (2.69) and standard deviation= (1.08), While the item number (50) which “Analyze and prioritize strengths and weaknesses of students.” comes at the last rank with mean= (2.53) and standard deviation= (1.03). Attributed to the stereotype of the school vision to students achievement as the determiner of evaluating performance for teachers.

The Collegiality and Professionalism Domain

Table 8 Mean & standard deviation of the collegiality and professionalism domain

No	Items	Mean	St. D	Rank	Level
57	Seek help and input from colleagues regarding specific classroom strategies and behaviors.	2.71	1.13	1	Medium
56	Promote positive interactions about students and parents.	2.63	1.11	2	Medium
58	Interact positively with colleagues by mentoring other teachers and sharing ideas and strategies.	2.59	1.07	3	Medium
59	Adhere to school instructions and procedures.	2.59	1.05	4	Medium
60	Work to achieve school and district improvement goals.	2.51	1.06	5	Medium

55	Interact to promote and support student learning.	2.47	1.04	6	Medium
	Total	2.58	0.38	-	Medium

As shown in table 8 the item number (57) which “Seek help and input from colleagues regarding specific classroom strategies and behaviors.” comes at the first rank with mean= (2.71) and standard deviation= (1.13), While the item number (55) which “Interact to promote and support student learning” comes at the last rank with mean= (2.47) and standard deviation= (1.04). Attributed to the old teachers have more experience than the new teachers, therefore newer teachers need their help.

Results Related to the Second Question:

Are there statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the averages of the performance of the secondary stage English teachers in the directorate of Irbid, first according to the Marzano scale attributed to the (gender, years of experience, educational level)?

To answer the question calculated Mean& standard deviation as in table 9:

Table 9 The Mean& standard deviation of the domain 1: classroom strategies and behaviors attributed to the gender, educational level and years of experience

Variable	Category		Classroom strategies and behaviors	Preparing and planning	Reflecting on teaching	Collegiality and professionalism
Gender	Male	Mean	2.58	2.62	2.67	2.59

		St. D	0.16	0.36	0.44	0.41
	Female	Mean	2.63	2.60	2.59	2.58
		St. D	0.15	0.34	0.36	0.36
Edu. Level	BA and above	Mean	2.60	2.64	2.67	2.59
		St. D	0.16	0.34	0.41	0.38
	BA and below	Mean	2.61	2.57	2.56	2.58
		St. D	0.15	0.37	0.38	0.38
Years of experience	Less than 5 years	Mean	2.58	2.57	2.68	2.55
		St. D	0.17	0.29	0.39	0.39
	5 – 10	Mean	2.61	2.57	2.54	2.64
		St. D	0.14	0.36	0.43	0.37
	More than 10 years	Mean	2.63	2.71	2.69	2.53
		St. D	0.14	0.39	0.35	0.38

As shown in table 9 there are apparent differences between the averages of the performance of the secondary stage English teachers in the directorate of Irbid, first according to the Marzano scale attributed to the (gender, years of experience, educational level), To see if these differences are statistically significant Three Way ANOVA Used as in table 10:

Table 10 Three Way ANOVA for differences between the averages of the performance of the secondary stage English teachers in the

directorate of Irbid, first according to the Marzano scale attributed to the (gender, years of experience, educational level)

Domain	Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Classroom Strategies and Behaviors	Gender	.021	1	.021	.937	.335
	Edu. Level	.004	1	.004	.159	.691
	Years of experience	.092	2	.046	2.047	.133
	Gender * Edu. Level	.100	1	.100	4.424	.037
	Gender * years of experience	.038	2	.019	.842	.433
	Edu. Level * Years of experience	.005	2	.003	.112	.894
	Gender * Edu.level * years of experience	.000	2	.000	.008	.992
	Error	3.545	157	.023		
	Corrected Total	3.973	168			
Preparing and Planning	Gender	.012	1	.012	.100	.752
	Edu. Level	.605	1	.605	4.936	.028
	Years of experience	.687	2	.343	2.802	.064
	Gender * Edu. Level	.267	1	.267	2.177	.142
	Gender * years of experience	.064	2	.032	.261	.771
	Edu. Level * years of experience	.168	2	.084	.686	.505

	Gender * Edu. level * years of experience	.012	2	.006	.047	.954
	Error	19.249	157	.123		
	Corrected Total	21.057	168			
Reflecting on Teaching	Gender	.044	1	.044	.273	.602
	Edu. Level	.667	1	.667	4.096	.045
	Years of experience	.861	2	.430	2.645	.074
	Gender * Edu. Level	.023	1	.023	.142	.707
	Gender * years of experience	.019	2	.010	.059	.942
	Edu. Level * years of experience	.090	2	.045	.277	.759
	Gender * Edu. Level * years of experience	.073	2	.037	.225	.799
	Error	25.548	157	.163		
	Corrected Total	27.296	168			
Collegiality and Professionalism	Gender	.020	1	.020	.134	.715
	Edu. Level	.017	1	.017	.113	.737
	Years of experience	.846	2	.423	2.854	.061
	Gender * Edu. Level	.033	1	.033	.222	.638
	Gender * years of experience	.588	2	.294	1.984	.141
	Edu. Level * years of experience	.316	2	.158	1.065	.347
	Gender * Edu. Level * years of experience	.011	2	.005	.036	.965

	Edu.level * years of experience					
	Error	23.272	157	.148		
	Corrected Total	24.729	168			
Total	Gender	.015	1	.015	1.061	.305
	Edu. Level	.071	1	.071	5.090	.025
	Years of experience	.116	2	.058	4.173	.017
	Gender * Edu. Level	.014	1	.014	1.024	.313
	Gender * years of experience	.009	2	.004	.311	.733
	Edu. Level * years of experience	.011	2	.006	.397	.673
	Gender * Edu.level * years of experience	.001	2	.001	.044	.957
	Error	2.186	157	.014		
	Corrected Total	2.442	168			

Table10: shows no Statistically differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the average and standard deviation according to teachers' responses to the classroom strategies and behaviors domain attributed to the gender, where (F) value= (1.061). But there are statistical differences attributed to educational level where (F) value= (5.090), and These differences are in favor of BA and above, Also there are statistical differences attributed to years of experience where (F) value= (4.173), and to know to whom these differences used Scheffe Multiple Comparisons as in table 11:

Table 11 Scheffe multiple comparisons, differences between the average and standard deviation according to teachers' responses to the classroom strategies and behaviors domain attributed to years of experience

(I) Experience	(J) Experience	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sigh.
Less than 5		-.0286	.02138	.410
	5-10 years	-.0728*	.02356	.010
	More than 10 years	-.0442	.02251	.149

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table11: shows differences between the average and standard deviation according to teachers' responses to the classroom strategies and behaviors domain attributed to Performance between (less than 5 years) and (More than 10 years) attributed for More than 10 years, Attributed to the teachers who have, years of experience are exposed to situations that make them more able to assess the performance of students.

Results of study:

The level of performance of secondary stage English teachers in the Directorate of Irbid, first according to Marzano's Teachers' Evaluation Model where comes medium with mean= (2.60) and

standard deviation= (0.12), and the domain (Reflecting on Teaching) comes at the first rank, with mean= (2.62) and standard deviation= (0.40), where the domain (Collegiality and Professionalism) comes at the last rank with mean= (2.58) and standard deviation = (0.38). Attributed to the school focusing on students' achievement as an essential factor in evaluating personal performance of the teacher and his ability to develop and execute the plans.

There are no statistically significant differences in ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the averages of the performance of the secondary stage English teachers in the Directorate of Irbid first on the Marzano Scale attributed to the gender. But there are statistical differences attributed to educational level in favor of BA and above, Also there are statistical differences attributed to years of experience between (less than 5 years) and (More than 10 years) attributed for More than 10 years. Attributed to the teachers who have, years of experience are exposed to situations that make them more able to assess the performance of students.

Recommendations:

- The Ministry of Education should hold training courses and workshops for of the English teachers to raising their performance in (Collegiality and Professionalism, Reflecting on Teaching, Preparing and Planning & Classroom Strategies and Behaviors) In particular Least experienced and qualified.
- The researcher recommends the ministry of education to use this card in evaluating English teachers' performance level to distinguish their evaluation from others.

- The researcher recommends that to enhance the positive environment should be enhanced through putting common plans between the teachers and parents.

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